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INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF RESEARCH –
GRANTHAALAYAH
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SPIRITUAL INTELLIGENCE AND PURPOSE IN LIFE OF SECONDARY SCHOOL TEACHERS

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Abstract

All around development means a person must be physically fit, mentally balanced, emotionally strong, socially adjusted and spiritually uplifted. The spiritual intelligence solves problems of meaning and value. It gives direction to our life in critical moment. Meaning/Purpose in life must be conceived in terms of the specific meaning of a personal life in a given situation. The study is design to examine the influence of the spiritual intelligence on purpose in life of secondary school teachers. The method used for the study is survey method. The sample of the study is 200 secondary school teachers. Two types of tools are used for this study. 1. The spiritual intelligence questionnaire constructed by Danah Zohar and Marshall (1999), it is a 5-point scale and 2. The purpose in life test prepared by Crumbaugh and Maholick (1969) is selected as an instrument to measure Viktor Frankl's concept in meaning in life. It is a 5 point Likert scale. Both the tools are used to collect the data from secondary school teachers.

The results of this study indicated that there is no significant difference is found in spiritual intelligence of secondary school teachers with below 10years, 10-20 years and 20 and above year's groups. No significant difference is found in purpose in life of secondary school teachers in their teaching experience with below 10years, 10-20 years and 20 and above year's groups. The variable teaching experience does not influence significantly the spiritual intelligence and purpose in life of secondary school teachers. The study showed that there is no significant association between the levels of spiritual intelligence of secondary school teachers and their purpose in life. Findings of this study shows that all secondary school teachers have average level of spiritual intelligence and purpose in life.

Keywords: Spiritual Intelligence; Secondary School Teachers and Purpose in Life.

Cite This Article: Dr. T. Swarupa Rani, and A. Siva Padmavathi. (2019). "SPIRITUAL INTELLIGENCE AND PURPOSE IN LIFE OF SECONDARY SCHOOL TEACHERS." *International Journal of Research - Granthaalayah*, 7(10), 26-34. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3522041>.

1. Introduction

Education is a life-long process by which an individual adapts himself/herself gradually and gracefully to the available physical, intellectual, emotional, social and spiritual environments. However, with developing knowledge about intelligence like intellectual Intelligence and emotional Intelligence, scientists said that neither intellectual intelligence nor emotional intelligence, separately or in combination is enough to explain to neither the full complexity of human intelligence nor the vast richness of the human soul and imagination. Bhangale and Mahajan (2013) say the ultimate goal of education is all round development of student. All around development means a person must be physically fit, mentally balanced, emotionally strong, socially adjusted and spiritually uplifted. The spiritual intelligence solves problems of meaning and value. It gives direction to our life in critical moment. Meaning/Purpose in life must be conceived in terms of the specific meaning of a personal life in a given situation. Life is a chain of questions which man has to answer by being responsible, by making decisions. Each question has only one answer, the right one. This does not imply that man is always capable of finding the true meaning to his existence. As a finite being he is not exempt from error but he has to try to reach the absolute rest.

Sound education is expected to provide ways and means for achieving the development of body, mind and spirit. No educational reform can be successful unless the quality of the teacher is improved. Teacher however, due to being endowed with the gift of understanding receives both praise for good actions, because they are caused by him. If a teacher achieves a noble purpose in life he will be deserving of praise and reward, and likewise if a teacher spends the precious days of his pursuing unworthy and selfish goals, he will be deserving of blame and punishment. The purpose in life is to grow and to learn and to make a better person.

2. Definitions

Various educationists defined spiritual intelligence and purpose in life in various ways.

Wolman (2001) "Spiritual intelligence is the human capacity to ask ultimate questions about the meaning of the life and to experience simultaneously the seamless connection between each one of us and the world in which we live".

Kate Diane Noble (2001) is of opinion that "Spiritual Intelligence is an innate human potential that can be a catalyst for psychological growth and healing. Spiritual Intelligence is not a static product, but a dynamic and fluid process that can transform one's personal and community life".

Frank J. Mac Hovee (2002) opines that "Spiritual Intelligence is a universal genetic personality trait worthy of further study, and presents a unified personality theory that encompasses previous and present theories and encourages their continued development".

Baumeister (1991) says Purpose in life is one of four fundamental ingredients of meaning the others being values, self-efficacy, and self-worth. He conceives of purpose as the process of connecting present events with those in the future and of using imagined the future events to find direction for present action".

Ryff's and Singer's (1998) "Purpose in life is a sense of one's life having a purpose or investing time and energy into the attainment of cherished goal".

From the above definitions spiritual intelligence is the human capacity to ask ultimate questions about the meaning of the life and purpose in life is the process of connecting present events with those in the future and of using imagined the future events to find direction for present action.

3. Need of the Study

The importance of human spiritual development has increasingly been considered in a few decades. The complexity of nowadays society and the increasing problems of the mechanical life, the changes in life styles and patterns in the postmodern era have caused human spiritual needs to fight against his material wishes and needs, and become more important. Spiritual intelligence can be used to identify and understand the thought patterns, beliefs and goals that form the foundation of our behavior. Spiritual intelligence is based on the fundamental ability of the human brain to create meanings, values, and beliefs. Spiritual intelligence refers to the measured spiritual abilities of a person such as being creative, insightful and believing in spiritual manifestation or religious beliefs as a guide in a way of life. Purpose in life is important to help the individual with the relief of anxiety and tension, spiritual intelligence also helps in overcoming his/her fears and anxieties. The teachers are the flywheels of the whole lively educational machine. If students are to develop their spiritual intelligence (SI), their teachers should be well-versed in these intelligences, so that they will be able to develop these qualities in their students.

4. Reviews

1) Researcher: Marzabadi et al. (2013)

Title: Relationship between organizational spirituality and spiritual intelligence with job burnout among a military university staffs.

Sample: 4452

Tool: Questionnaire

Findings: There was no significant difference between male and female participants in organizational spirituality. 2. Education could not cause any significant difference in organizational spirituality.

2) Researcher: Mandeep Kaur (2013)

Title: Spiritual intelligence of secondary school teachers in relation to their job satisfaction.

Sample: 100

Tool: Questionnaire (Spiritual Quotient Scale - Koradia, Singhal and Narang, 2008)

Findings: 1. Findings of the study revealed a significant positive relationship between teachers' spiritual intelligence and their job satisfaction. 2. A significant difference is found between spiritual intelligence of government and private secondary school teachers. 3. The study indicated that spiritual intelligence and job satisfaction are not influenced by gender.

3) Researcher: Jafari et al (2014)

Title: Comparison of relation between body image and spiritual intelligence among male and female students.

Sample: 376

Tool: Questionnaire (Spiritual intelligence scale (SSI-29))

Findings: the relation between Understanding and Communication with the Source of Existence with body image in male is significant, while it is not significant in female students. There are no significant difference between females' and males' scores in body image and spiritual intelligence.

4) Researcher: Stegar, Fitch-Martin, Donnely and Rickard (2014)

Title: Association between meaning in life and risking behaviours (i.e., substance use), of European American undergraduate students.

Sample: 571

Tool: Questionnaire (meaning in life by Steger, Frazier, Oishi & Keler, 2006)

Findings: Higher meaning in life reduced engagement in health risking behaviours.

5) Researcher: Pasarra and Kleftaras (2013)

Title: Role of meaning/purpose in life and depression in adaptation to physical disability

Sample: 511

Tool: Questionnaire (Life Attitude Profile by Reker, 1992).

Findings: Meaning/Purpose in life reduced the physical disability and made people easy with adaptation towards physical disability.

5. Operational Definitions

Spiritual intelligence: "Spiritual intelligence is the multiple ways of knowing and integrating the inner life of mind and spirit with the outer life of work in the world. To do our work successfully, we need a strategy how mind and spirit optimally involve finishing the work. Our mind operates thinking and feeling when doing the work. Thinking is used to process logic, writing, numbers, language, analysis, arithmetic, and order, while feeling is used to process creativity, concept, music, image, dimension, emotion, and shape. In other words, when the process of thinking operates together with feeling, the optimal results of our work will be gained" - **Vaughan (2004)**.

Purpose in life: "Purpose in life is the motivational dimension of meaning. He asserts that the "will to meaning" is a significant and universal human motive. Human are not merely biological, social, and psychological beings but also spiritual being capable transcending physical limitations through meaning and spirituality"- **Frankl**.

Secondary school teachers: A teacher who teaches VIII Class to X Class in Secondary schools.

6. Objectives of the Study

- 1) To find out the spiritual intelligence of secondary school teachers and to classify them.
- 2) To find out the spiritual intelligence of secondary school teachers with respect to their teaching experience.
- 3) To find out the purpose in life of secondary school teachers and to classify them.
- 4) To find out the purpose in life of secondary school teachers with respect to their teaching experience.
- 5) To find out the association between the levels of spiritual intelligence and purpose in life of secondary school teachers.

Hypotheses of the Study

- 1) Secondary school teachers differ in their levels of spiritual intelligence.

- 2) Teaching experience makes a significant difference in the spiritual intelligence of secondary school teachers.
- 3) Secondary school teachers differ in their levels of purpose in life.
- 4) Teaching experience makes a significant difference in the purpose in life of secondary school teachers.
- 5) There is an association between the levels of spiritual intelligence of secondary school teachers and their purpose in life.

Sample

A random sample of 200 secondary school teachers is taken for this study.

Methodology

Normative survey method is followed to study this problem. Survey method is found to be relevant to collect data from spiritual intelligence and purpose in life of secondary school teachers.

Tools Used

Two types of tools are used for this study.

- 1) **Spiritual intelligence:** A questionnaire on spiritual intelligence constructed by Danah Zohar and Marshall (1999) was used to collect the data from teachers. There are altogether 78 items against which 5 alternatives are given. The points are strongly agree, agree, undecided, disagree and strongly disagree. It is a standardized questionnaire and it is reliable and valid.
- 2) **Purpose-in-life:** To measure the purpose in life of secondary school teachers, the purpose in life test prepared by Crumbaugh and Maholick (1969) was selected as an instrument to measure Viktor Frankl's concept in meaning in life. The purpose-in-life test consists of 20 items. (e.g., "My personal existence is: Utterly Meaningless and without purpose", "Neutral" and "Very purposeful and meaningful"). A 7- point Likert scale ranging from 1 to 7 (specific statements between 1 through 7 vary from item to item) i.e., 1 (low purpose or low score) to 7 (high purpose or high score). It is a standardized questionnaire and it is reliable and valid.

Statistical Techniques

The data is analyzed through the statistical techniques like mean, % of mean, standard deviation, t-test and Chi-square test of association.

7. Analysis of Data

Objective-I: To find out the spiritual intelligence of secondary school teachers and to classify them.

In analyzing data answer for the first objective Mean, SD, % of Mean of scores of total sample of teachers in spiritual intelligence and tabulated in table 1 and 2.

Table 1.1: Spiritual intelligence of secondary school teachers

Whole Sample (200)	Mean	SD	% of Mean
	282.27	65.32	141.1

Interpretation: From the table it is observed that the mean on spiritual intelligence scores of 200 secondary school teachers is 282.27, % of mean is 141.1 and SD is 65.32.

To obtain the levels of spiritual intelligence of secondary school teachers, the following procedure is followed.

Procedure: One standard deviation is added to the mean. The obtained value is 347.59 (Mean + 1 SD = 282.26+65.32=347.59). The number of teachers whose scores are above 349 (rounded off) is arrived at (51) and converted into percentage (25.5). This group is considered to have high spiritual intelligence.

One standard deviation is subtracted from the mean. The obtained value is 216.95 (Mean - 1 SD = 282.26-65.32=216.95). The number of teachers whose scores are below 217 (rounded off) is arrived at (21) and converted into percentage (10.5). This group is considered to have low spiritual intelligence.

The number of teachers whose scores are in between 217 and 349 are considered to possess average spiritual intelligence.

Table-1.2: Levels of spiritual Intelligence of secondary school teachers

S. No	Levels of SI	Score	N	Percentage
1	High SI	217 and Below	51	25.5
2	Average SI	217-349	128	64
3	Low SI	349 and Above	21	10.5

Interpretation: From the tables 1.1 and 1.2 it can be inferred that the sample secondary school teachers have average level of spiritual Intelligence. Twenty five point five percent (25.5) of secondary school teachers have high level of spiritual intelligence. Sixty four percent (64) of secondary school teachers have average level of spiritual intelligence. Only 10.5% of secondary school teachers have low level of spiritual intelligence.

Objective-2: To find out the spiritual intelligence of secondary school teachers with respect to their teaching Experience.

Table 2:

S.NO	Variable	Groups	N	Mean	SD	% of Mean	SED	t
1	Teaching Experience	Below 10 years	169	282.27	65.32	141.13	14.20	0.116*
		10-20 years	25	283.93	66.45	141.96		
2		10-20 years	25	283.93	66.45	141.96	30.60	0.029 *
		20 and Above years	06	283.02	67.53	141.5		

3	Below 10 years	169	282.27	65.32	141.13	28.02	0.026 *
	20 and Above years	06	283.02	67.53	141.5		

*Not significant at 0.05 level

Interpretation: The obtained t values are less than the table value 1.96 at 0.05 level. Hence, they are not significant at 0.05 level. Therefore, the null hypothesis is accepted. No significant difference is found in spiritual intelligence of secondary school teachers with below 10years, 10-20 years and 20 and above year's groups. The variable teaching experience does not influence significantly the spiritual intelligence of secondary school teachers.

Objective-3: To find out the purpose in life of secondary school teachers and to classify them. In analyzing data answer for the first objective Mean, SD, % of Mean of scores of total sample of teachers in purpose in life and tabulated in table 3.1 and 3.2.

Table 3.1: Purpose in life of secondary school teachers

Whole Sample (200)	Mean	SD	% of Mean
	82.32	22.05	41.16

Interpretation: From the table it is observed that the mean on purpose in life scores of 200 secondary school teachers is 82.32, % of mean is 41.16 and SD is 22.05.

To obtain the levels of purpose in life of secondary school teachers, the following procedure is followed.

Procedure: One standard deviation is added to the mean. The obtained value is 104.37 (Mean + 1 SD = 82.32+22.05=104.37). The number of teachers whose scores are above 104 (rounded off) is arrived at (30) and converted into percentage (15). This group is considered to have high purpose in life.

One standard deviation is subtracted from the mean. The obtained value is 60 (Mean - 1 SD = 82.32-22.05=60). The number of teachers whose scores are below 60(rounded off) is arrived at (17) and converted into percentage (8.5). This group is considered to have low purpose in life. The number of teachers whose scores are in between 60 and 104 are considered to possess average purpose in life.

Table 3: Levels of purpose in life of secondary school teachers

S. No	Levels of PIL	Score	N	Percentage
1	High PIL	104 and Above	30	15
2	Average PIL	60-104	153	76.5
3	Low PIL	60 and below	17	8.5

Interpretation: From the tables 3.1 and 3.2 it can be inferred that the sample secondary school teachers have average level of purpose in life. Fifteen percent (15) of secondary school teachers have high level of purpose in life. Seventy six point five percent (76.5) of secondary school teachers have average level of purpose in life. Only 8.5% of secondary school teachers have low level of purpose in life.

Objective-4: To find out the purpose in life of secondary school teachers with respect to their teaching experience

Table 4:

S.NO	Variable	Groups	N	Mean	SD	% of Mean	SED	t
1	Teaching Experience	Below 10 years	169	82.32	22.02	41.16	5.16	0.620*
		10-20 years	25	85.52	25.86	42.76		
2		10-20 years	25	85.52	25.86	42.76	10.71	0.278
		20 and Above years	06	82.54	22.98	41.27		
3		Below 10 years	169	82.32	22.02	41.16	9.53	0.023 *
		20 and Above years	06	82.54	22.98	41.27		

*Not significant at 0.05 level

Interpretation: The obtained t values are less than the table value 1.96 at 0.05 level. Hence, they are not significant at 0.05 level. Therefore, the null hypothesis is accepted.

No significant difference is found in purpose in life of secondary school teachers in their teaching experience with below 10years, 10-20 years and 20 and above year's groups.

The variable teaching experience is not influencing significantly the purpose in life of secondary school teachers.

Objective-5: To find out the association between the levels of spiritual intelligence and purpose in life.

Table 5:

PIL/ SI	High SI	Average SI	Low SI	TOTAL	χ^2 value	Table value
High PIL	10(7.65)	14(19.2)	06(3.15)	30	7.267 *	9.488
Average PIL	38(39.01)	103(97.92)	12(16.06)	153		
Low PIL	03(4.33)	11(10.88)	03(1.78)	17		
TOTAL	51	128	21	200		

*Not significant at 0.05 level

Interpretation: The obtained chi-square (χ^2) value (7.267) is less than the table value (9.488) at 0.05 level for a df of 4. Therefore, it is not significant at 0.05 level. Hence, the null hypothesis is accepted. That means there is no significant association between the levels of spiritual intelligence and levels of purpose in life of secondary school teachers.

8. Educational Implications

- 1) The results of this study may be extended to the teachers at different levels.
- 2) Results of this study may be useful to plan various in-service programmes for the teachers.

9. Suggestions for Further Research

- 1) This study is limited to secondary school teachers but this may be extended to the teachers and students at various levels, employees of different professors.

- 2) Further study can be taken up by increasing the sample size, different dimensions of spiritual intelligence, with different tools constructed by other educationists etc.
- 3) Longitudinal and experimental studies can also be carried out on spiritual intelligence.
- 4) Experimental and correlative studies with other psychological aspects may also be carried out.

10. Conclusion

The researchers in this field believed that when the level of Spiritual Intelligence is high, we are in contact with our wholeness and we tend to develop intellectual and proper behavior. When the level of our Spiritual Intelligence is low, we become caricatures of ourselves. A teacher with high level of Spiritual Intelligence can provide guidelines for living from a soul-level and attaining self-fulfillment in both one's work and private life. Teachers have strong hand in shaping the child's value systems. A teacher with high Spiritual Intelligence in himself can develop them into good personalities. The spiritual intelligence provides a general basis for the individual to be able to consider his seeking for goals and meaning/purpose in life, and to move in the direction of the aims which are personally meaningful. It aids the individual in directing his/her concerns to the wider image and in focusing, consciously, his/her activities in a context that is wider.

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